

basis of constraints prevailing in rice production. The upper domain experiences severe water deficit and soil

acidification whereas the lower domain has excess water and soil salinization. Technology generation processes, such as

varietal improvement programs, need to make location-specific recommendations for the identified domains. ■

Postharvest technology

Delay in threshing and mode of beating effects on milling recovery

A. Ali, M. A. Karim, L. Ali, S. S. Ali, M. Jamil, and A. Majid, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

Harvested rice in the Punjab, Pakistan, is usually left in the field to dry in loose bundles for a few days before threshing. We assessed how a delay in threshing affected milling recovery of commercial

varieties KS282 (medium grain) and Basmati 385 (fine grain) from 1988 to 1990. We compared the traditional hand-threshing techniques of beating rice against a bund, steel drum, or wooden log.

The rice was harvested at the optimum maturity stage and left in the field in loose bundles of uniform size (40 plants, with about 20 tillers/plant) for 0, 2, 4, and 6 d before threshing. The difference in day and night temperature was about

15 °C, which resulted in repeated drying and wetting of the rice. Rice samples were sun-dried to the optimum moisture content and milled.

Threshing grain on the day of harvest gave the highest head rice recovery and the lowest broken rice (see table). The recovery decreased with delay in threshing. The differences between delays of 0 and 2 d were not significant in either variety (see table). Differences in mode of beating did not significantly affect milling recovery. ■

Milling recovery at different threshing times and modes of beating. Punjab, Pakistan, 1988-90.^a

Delay in threshing after harvesting (d)	Head rice (%)					Broken rice (%)				
	Beating on bund	Beating on steel drum	Beating on wooden log	Mean	Decrease in head rice	Beating on bund	Beating on steel drum	Beating on wooden log	Mean	Increase in broken rice
<i>KS282</i>										
0	55.7	56.0	55.6	55.8 a	-	15.0	14.6	16.0	15.2 a	-
2	55.3	55.7	54.9	55.3 a	0.5	15.7	15.8	17.0	16.2 a	1.0
4	53.0	53.5	52.7	53.1 b	2.7	17.4	18.0	18.6	18.0 b	2.8
6	49.6	49.0	49.5	49.4 c	6.4	21.0	22.0	21.2	21.4 c	6.2
Mean	53.4 a	53.5 a	53.2 a	-	-	17.3 a	17.6 a	18.2 a	-	-
<i>Basmati 385</i>										
0	53.0	52.5	53.3	52.9 a	-	17.0	16.7	16.8	16.8 a	-
2	52.1	52.0	52.5	52.2 a	0.7	17.3	18.0	17.7	17.7 a	0.9
4	49.6	50.4	51.0	50.3 b	2.6	20.0	19.8	18.0	19.3 b	2.5
6	47.0	47.2	46.5	46.9 c	6.0	23.0	22.6	22.6	22.7 c	5.9
Mean	50.4 a	50.5 a	50.8 a	-	-	19.3 a	19.3 a	19.2 a	-	-

^aResults are av of 3 yr. Means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Announcements

Outstanding young women in rice science award

The Outstanding Young Women in Rice Science (OYWRS) Award is the foremost international recognition of the important contributions women are making to rice research and agriculture. The biennial award was established in 1990 by IRRI to encourage the participation of women in rice research and to promote their professional development.

Presentation of award

The 1994 presentation will be part of the International Rice Research Conference (IRRC), tentatively set for April 1994 in Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. Awardees receive a recognition plaque and a travel grant to attend IRRC. Each awardee must present a scientific paper on her research.

Criteria

The award is presented to individuals who are 40 years of age or younger (born on 1 Jan 1954 or later for the 1994 program) and actively conducting research in any endeavor of rice science in a public or private institution in the five regions of the world's major rice-producing areas. Recipients are selected by regions: Africa, South Asia, West Asia, Southeast Asia, and Latin America and the Caribbean. Awards are made